

The Emperor’s New Clothes: A Manifesto for Universities in an AI-Haunted World [Extended Abstract]

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Abstract

Universities face an existential crisis revealed, but not caused, by artificial intelligence. Using Lakatos’ Philosophy of Science, we argue higher education has become a degenerating research programme, maintaining formal structures while abandoning educational substance. Drawing on evidence from an experimental AI-integrated unit at Macquarie University, we pose three interlocking questions: What constitutes content-increasing education when AI handles information transfer? How can universities reconnect education to meaningful world-making? What academic practices enable transformative rather than transactional learning? Student transformations documented in our unit suggest design principles for post-transactional universities that embrace productive failure, reward process mastery, and develop new capabilities beyond credentialism.

1 Introduction

Universities face an existential crisis that predates but is revealed by artificial intelligence. This chapter employs Lakatos’ (1992) philosophy of research programmes

to argue that higher education has become a degenerating programme, maintaining formal structures while hollowing out educational substance. We pose three interlocking open questions that emerge from the disconnect between what universities claim to offer and what they actually deliver. Drawing on evidence from an experimental AI-integrated unit at Macquarie University, we explore how Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) serves as both diagnostic tool and potential catalyst for transformation.

2 The ‘Degenerating Research Programme’ of Universities

Defenses of the current pedagogical purposes of universities exhibit what Lakatos terms “content-decreasing” explanations of the core “hypotheses” of what it means to be a university. Content-decreasing explanations provide auxiliary hypotheses which serve merely as “linguistic devices” to protect a failing hard core of assumptions (Lakatos et al., 1992, p. 34), rather than adding facts and context to grow our understanding of a research discipline. In an academic sense, we can see the linguistic (business) turn where extreme emphasis on retention, and a focus on hyper-efficiency when grading have seemed to miss the point of the actual *teaching*. We can consider these ancillary value statements auxiliary hypotheses in support of the value of a university to students.

The commodification of education has created what Eaton and Christensen Hughes (2022) describes as a “farical transaction where the players pay lip service to the quest for knowledge while engaging in a transaction whereby time and money are exchanged for credentials” (p. 220). This transactional model manifests in multiple symptoms that predate AI’s emergence. When the fundamental assumptions (the hard core of hypotheses) of university administrators must serve the business interests of the university first and the expectations of a smooth ride by the students if they tick the boxes and pay lip service to assignments second, the explanations which serve to defend the present reality in terms of effective learning increasingly resemble a degenerating research programme (i.e. Lakatos’ example of astrology).

Grade inflation exemplifies this degeneration. Chowdhury (2018) documents how “grade inflation has become the norm in many colleges and universities around the world,” noting that “if grades are a form of academic currency, then grade inflation results in the devaluation of that currency.” Universities face enrolment pressures that incentivise lowering standards rather than improving education. Students transfer to institutions “where high grades are easily awarded,” creating a race to the bottom. And, the same pressure on faculty is not to be underestimated: grades too high earn complaints from colleagues, grades too low earn poor feedback from students (jeopardising promotion) and the endless paperwork of grade appeals.

Furthermore, students’ expectation of “practical content” reflects what Priego (2025) identifies as students’ desire for “definitive answers—not inquiry.” This preference for bullet-point delivery over critical engagement stems from understandable systemic pressures. Students working full-time while studying full-time lack opportunities for what Breen (2025) calls “focused intellectual work.” Universities respond

by cramming more content into fewer units, operating under the false assumption that sufficient “good enough” and “focused enough” and “quick enough” content delivery prevents failure or attrition. The underlying hypothesis here, is that this commodification of academia provides a good education at an affordable price.

Contract cheating services, essay mills, and systematic disengagement predated November 2022’s release of ChatGPT 3.5 by a decade (Eaton & Christensen Hughes, 2022; Lancaster, 2020; Rigby et al., 2015; Walker & Townley, 2012). These represent (just some of a range of) rational responses to a system that rewards credential acquisition over learning (Sungur, 2007). Students correctly regulate their effort when universities signal that going through the motions suffices (Burns et al., 2025). Critical thinking becomes a gesture performed within prescribed boundaries, never threatening the underlying transactional model.

AI’s emergence makes this degeneration undeniable, even to the public. When machines can complete our assessments better than students, give better in-class feedback, and give comments back to the students of the same quality of underresourced markers, the protective belt of auxiliary hypotheses of the value of a university education collapses. The emperor’s nakedness becomes visible to all. Yet this revelation also opens possibilities for transformation.

Our experiences teaching a unit on the pragmatics of AI using a disciplinary lens revealed how students’ encounters with large language models generated fundamental questions about education’s purpose and practice. These questions emerged not from theoretical speculation but from students discovering unknown-to-them capabilities. Fundamentally, effective prompting, the performance of those prompts to their colleagues, and their own self-reflection on prompt quality forced them to be able to articulate their ideas and their needs, as well as realise capabilities demanded by ambitions that they had not previously brought together across their disparate classes.

3 Three Interlocking Open Questions

Our analysis draws from student experiences in ARTS3500, the capstone unit in the Bachelor of Arts at Macquarie University in 2024. We assumed responsibility for several discipline-based streams within this unit to explore AI applications in specific topical areas. While the capstone approach traditionally consolidates disciplinary expertise, students’ lived experiences revealed an unexpected freedom. They used their expertise to ask transdisciplinary questions that emerged naturally from their engagement with AI.

Students approached problems differently than we anticipated. Rather than starting from disciplinary perspectives, they began with larger complex questions and challenges. Their confidence in moving beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries arose organically through AI use, not through traditional lectures.

This shift occurred across diverse student projects. An entire stream developed simulations and wargames, explored US Cold War history (the geopolitics shaping the cold war being novel to Australian students), and generated transdisciplinary questions that paradoxically strengthened their disciplinary practice. Student experiences revealed transformations that existing pedagogical frameworks cannot adequately

explain. Class transcripts and assessments¹ document these journeys. Those who began as AI sceptics developed sophisticated approaches to knowledge creation when freed from traditional assessment constraints. Not to say that all of them were wholesale adopters of AI for everything. On the contrary, students in this unit had much more nuanced judgement of *when and how* to use AI to accomplish their own, individual, goals.

Rather than racing through material for students to regurgitate as proof of learning, we dwelt in process: the critical and pragmatic use of AI itself. This shift from content mastery to process engagement created space for deeper enquiry. When freed from traditional assessments that demand students echo prescribed knowledge back to teachers, they developed sophisticated approaches to knowledge creation of their own.

Their case studies in this volume document remarkable journeys. Students moved from viewing AI as an existential threat to understanding it as an intellectual tool that amplifies rather than replaces human capability. These documented transformations generate three fundamental questions about the future of university education.

3.1 What constitutes education in an AI-saturated world?

Traditional pedagogies assume knowledge transfer from expert to novice through structured content delivery. This model fails when AI can access and synthesise information more efficiently than any lecturer. Our students discovered they could ask sophisticated, transdisciplinary questions only when freed from disciplinary boundaries and assessment constraints. As one student noted, they “ended up asking the sorts of questions that you would want someone trained in IR and in politics to be able to ask...way outside disciplinary boundaries.”

Lakatos et al. (1992) describes the demarcation problem of science as:

This demarcation between progressive and degenerating problem-shifts sheds new light on the appraisal of scientific – or rather, progressive – explanations. If we put forward a theory to resolve a contradiction between a previous theory and a counterexample in such a way that the new theory, instead of offering a content-increasing (scientific) explanation, only offers a content-decreasing (linguistic) reinterpretation, the contradiction is resolved in a merely semantical, unscientific way. (p. 34)

To move away from the degenerative defenses of the transactional university experience, new core hypotheses of the value of a university education must be advanced. We suggest education must shift from content delivery to capability development in more ambitious ways than it has so far. To be clear, little of what we have said here is a novel critique of the modern university. Academics have been trying to solve for these tensions for decades. However, time-poor, stressed, or recalcitrant academics default back to the content-delivery approaches they feel most comfortable with. A traditional class will always find tension between the expectations of content delivery imposed by the timetable and the aspirations of capability development dreamt of in course redesigns. We suggest that borrowing the idea of apprenticeship learning in a university context may help break free from traditional lecture and tutorial delivery.

¹available at the Australian Data Archive for reuse under Macquarie University ethics approval 16084

Billett’s (2016) conception of apprenticeship learning offers insights here. He argues that “most occupational preparation has arisen through apprenticeship as a mode of learning... mainly through learners’ active and interdependent engagement in occupational tasks, not through being taught or directly guided.” In the university context, AI use offers this opportunity for engagement (while risking severe disengagement) and allowing university classes to exist on a spectrum between apprenticeship for those most engaged and the passive reception of tutorial content for risk and engagement-adverse students.

Breen (2023) asserts that “LLMs are deeply, inherently textual. And they are reliant on text in a way that is directly linked to the skills and methods that we emphasize in university humanities classes.” (Rather than threatening these textual skills, effective AI use amplifies them. The question becomes: how do we design pedagogies that use AI to enhance rather than replace intellectual development? How do we create moments where, as one student reflects later in this volume, AI became “ready-to-hand” through sustained practice with expert guidance.

Our evidence suggests this requires embracing productive failure as method. Students need to discover epistemological boundaries through exploration, not instruction. Process-based assessment that values thinking over outputs becomes essential. What fundamental assumptions about efficiency, scalability, and standardisation in mass education must change to be able to teach students in our current reality?

3.2 How can universities reconnect education to world-making?

The capability development question leads naturally to considering purpose. If universities must shift from content delivery to capability building, what capabilities matter and why? Universities claim to prepare students for meaningful participation in society. Yet the disconnect between academic exercises and real-world impact grows ever wider. Authentic assessment advocates like Wiggins (as cited in Vilalta-Perdomo et al., 2025) emphasise tasks that “represent how knowledge and skills are used in real-life settings” requiring students to “use judgment and inventiveness to solve unstructured situations.”

Our students thrived when given problems without predetermined disciplinary framings. Students did not fear or realise the complexity of the challenges before entering into them. Only through failure and iteration did they resolve the scope, complexity, and multi-faceted/disciplinary nature of the tasks they took on themselves (sometimes to their own chagrin). This unfolding aligns with problem-based learning approaches, yet differs crucially in refusing to bound problems within academic categories. Real-world challenges rarely respect disciplinary boundaries.

The situation grows urgent as AI handles routine cognitive tasks. If universities continue producing graduates trained for work AI already performs better, a significant part of what they say they offer students evaporates. The alternative requires fundamental restructuring around project-based learning at programme rather than unit level. Students should develop portfolios of real accomplishments rather than transcripts of completed courses. Project failure (and iteration) should be a badge of resiliency rather than an indictment of the student’s fundamental worth to society.

How many business projects fail? In the right circumstances, with appropriate psychological safety and time to reflect, students can learn more from ambitious failure than conservative success.

The guild model of earlier centuries (apprentice, journeyman, master) offers historical precedent for education through participation in consequential work. Apprentices learned by contributing to actual production under master guidance. While skilled trades maintain this approach today, we argue that universities could adapt these interaction and learning patterns for higher education contexts. Modern internships gesture toward this model but remain peripheral to core academic programmes. What would universities look like if student work created real value beyond grades?

3.3 What academic practices enable transformative rather than transactional learning?

Even if we identify the right capabilities and connect them to meaningful purposes, implementation remains challenging. Current academic structures actively resist the transformative practices our evidence suggests are necessary (Rosenberg, 2023). Current academic labour structures incentivise efficient content delivery over transformative engagement. Marking essays on familiar topics has 20 minutes budgeted per essay; guiding authentic inquiry takes hours and can be spread over far fewer students per academic. The economics of mass education push toward standardisation exactly when personalisation becomes essential.

Our experimental unit required intensive engagement. We reviewed student prompts live in class weekly, spending half an hour of “valuable” class time providing individualised feedback. We adapted teaching and our assessments continuously to emerging insights from the student’s experimentation. This apprenticeship-style teaching within university structures proved transformative but shattered scalability imperatives baked into the present budget process.

Technology and access to frontier large language models offers partial solutions. AI can amplify the personalisation and scaffolding needed to answer some of these questions of exploration and productive failure at scale, freeing academics for higher-level engagement and feedback. But, this shift in the university’s research programme requires academics to develop new capabilities. Facilitating inquiry, especially using AI services which change almost monthly, fundamentally differs from delivering lectures on well-tread and safe topics. Guiding productive failure differs from marking correct answers. The question becomes: how do we transform academic practice while acknowledging economic and institutional constraints?

4 Toward a Manifesto

These open questions reveal a choice. Universities can continue their degenerating programme, adding ever more elaborate auxiliary hypotheses to justify credentialism. Or they can brave new approaches that treat AI as catalyst for long-overdue transformation. These new approaches (most will fail) may serve to introduce new facts and context to the question of: “What should a university do in regards to the education of its students?”

The student transformations we documented suggest a path which holds promise. Our evidence suggests engaged students hunger for genuine engagement when given structures that reward risk-taking over compliance. They can develop sophisticated critical capabilities when freed from artificial constraints. The challenge lies in scaling these insights within institutional realities.

Rather than prescribe definitive answers, we offer design principles derived from our open questions. A post-transactional university might:

- Rapidly transition between content delivery and capability development;
- Connect all learning to real-world impact (beyond token employability gestures);
- Reward process mastery over output production;
- Embrace productive failure as pedagogy; and
- Develop new forms of social proof beyond grades.

The emperor's new clothes have been revealed. Our experiments at Macquarie suggest students already see through the illusion. They demonstrated remarkable capabilities when we stopped pretending that content delivery equals education. The question now is whether universities will acknowledge their nakedness and clothe themselves in pedagogies fitted to our AI-haunted world, or continue parading in their invisible finery while students and society politely look away.

AI Use Disclosure

Claude 3.7 Sonnet and Claude 4 Opus were instrumental in the creation of this text, using techniques being currently developed by Ballsun-Stanton in his paper *An Absence of Judgement: AI's Limitations in Deep Research tasks* by Ballsun-Stanton and Ross (preprint links forthcoming). Prompts and logs of AI use are available at https://osf.io/gm9qz/?view_only=56e6db3191974ee5812f163503f42fad

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